

Validation and operational application of the hybrid NeQuick-TaD 3D ionospheric electron density reconstruction model

Anna Belehaki, George Stamatakis, Themistokles Herekakis, Angeliki Thanasou

Ionospheric Group, Institute of Astronomy Astrophysics Space Applications and Remote Sensing, National Observatory of Athens, Greece

Abstract

The current study presents the hybrid NeQuick-TaD (HyNT) 3D ionospheric electron density reconstruction model, which is based on the TaD extrapolation concept applied over the bottomside 3D electron density grids, calculated with the NeQuick model and updated with Digisonde data. For the validation of the model, the results obtained for the European middle-latitude region, are compared with COSMIC-2 RO (Radio Occultation) data and with in situ Swarm electron density data. The relative performance of the HyNT model and of the standard IRI2020 climate model and the F2-peak constrained IRI2020 model is assessed based on the mean absolute error (MAE) obtained over the statistical sample of data available from 2023 to 2025. The results indicate that the model performance depends on the altitude, while it is assumed that some degradation maybe due to the legacy core models for the scale height and transition height forming the core of the TaD formulation. Another point for future investigation is the dependence of the TaD core model from data not directly observed but calculated, such as the automatic scaled Digisonde profiles and the TEC, while the standard IRI is based on smooth median values that smooth potential offsets.

1. Introduction

Accurate modeling of the vertical electron density distribution in the ionosphere and plasmasphere remains a core challenge in space weather research and operational forecasting (Hoque et al., 2022; Belehaki et al., 2017; Stankov et al., 2003; Pignalberi et al., 2018).

Operational systems such as HF communication systems, satellite navigation and positioning systems, HF direction finding systems and over the horizon radars require advanced models that bridge the gap between climatological averages and real-time ionospheric states, ultimately supporting improved performance and decision-making in space weather-sensitive applications (Kintner et al., 2007; Cannon, 2013; Liu et al., 2021; Buzulukova and Tsurutani, 2022).

Recent model advances demonstrate impressive capability to ingest and assimilate data from all possible sources, however their performance underscores the need to significant

improvements, especially under disturbances and irregularities (Themens et al., 2017; Shim et al., 2011; 2018).

The International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) is an empirical standard model that provides median ionospheric parameters—such as electron density, electron temperature, and ion composition—at different altitudes, locations, times, and solar activity conditions. Developed under the auspices of the Committee on Space Research (COSPAR) and the International Union of Radio Science (URSI), IRI is widely used for ionospheric forecasting, space weather research, and radio propagation studies, directly for predictions and often as background model. The latest version of the model is IRI-2020 which delivers monthly median conditions based on long-term averages. As being a climatological model, IRI does not capture ionospheric disturbances or irregularities. From various studies, comparing to ionosondes, incoherent scatter radars, topside sounders, and in situ data from LEO satellites, it is resulted that the RMS error in Ne(h) is $\sim 10\text{--}20\%$ at F2 peak (NeF2) under quiet conditions and the error in hmF2 is $\sim \pm 20\text{--}30$ km typically (Bilitza et al., 2022). In general, the accuracy decreases during geomagnetic storms, at equatorial anomaly regions, and for irregular structures (MSTIDs, plasma bubbles).

NeQuick is another broadly used electron density reconstruction model. The latest version of the NeQuick model, typically referred to as NeQuick 2 (Nava et al., 2008; Radicella and Nava, 2010; Kashcheyev & Nava, 2019), is an empirical model of the electron density profile (Ne) from ground to $\sim 20,000$ km (covering the ionosphere and plasmasphere). It is driven by solar activity indices, most often effective sunspot number (R_{12}) or global TEC. NeQuick is designed for quiet-time ionospheric conditions, for average behavior across seasons and solar cycles. The model produces smooth, climatological profiles using a 3-segment semi-Epstein function. NeQuick is used as a topside modeling option in IRI.

Pignalberi et al. (2025) investigated the performance of the IRI-2020 model in describing the topside ionosphere electron density variations through its four topside modeling options by comparison with in-situ observations by GRACE, ICON, and DMSP F15 LEO satellites.

IRI-2001cor2 model remarkably improved the description of the latitudinal variation of the topside electron density at low latitudes and for the LTs associated to the EIA phenomenology, accounting for the observed shift of EIA crests towards the geomagnetic equator with increasing altitude. The largest improvement by IRI-2001cor2 is for the lowest altitudes investigated by this study (400–600 km), while at the highest altitudes (830–850 km) it performs similar to IRI-NeQuick; IRI-2001cor2 model showed a solar activity trend at DMSP F15 altitude, thus signifying a solar activity variation not accounted for by the model. Moreover, the comparison at different QD latitudes evidenced that anchor points at low latitudes set latitudinal variations showing a relative maximum at the geomagnetic equator and relative minima at around $\pm 15^\circ$ QD latitude, with sharp transitions between these latitudinal ranges.

IRI-NeQuick model showed consistent performance at different altitudes but with the well-established issues connected to the representation of the low-latitude topside ionosphere. Due to the link between the bottomside and topside thickness parameters in the NeQuick formulation, the model shows latitudinal features associated to the F2-layer peak behavior also in the upper topside and in the plasmaspheric extension, which largely disagrees with observations.

Themens et al. (2017) have diagnosed shortcomings in the NeQuick topside model and its parameterization at high and upper middle latitudes, showing that not only are there errors in the NeQuick's modeling of the monthly median topside scale height by up to 60 km but that there are also fundamental concerns regarding the shape of the topside model itself.

Another approach for the topside reconstruction modeling comes with the development of the Topside Sounder Model assisted by Digisonde (TaD) (Kutiev et al., 2009a;b). The TaD model uses the Topside Sounders Model (TSM) as a core empirical model for the O^+/H^+ transition height (hT) and the topside scale height (HT), derived from vertical electron density profiles from Alouette and ISIS topside sounders. These parameters are strongly correlated (correlation > 0.8 in midlatitudes), allowing their ratio ($RT = HT/hT$) to be used as a proxy in model tuning. The first version of the model (TaDv1) employed a two-part analytic formulation: an α -Chapman profile up to hT and an exponential H^+ profile above.

Further upgrades introduced in TaDv2 and TaDv3 (Belehaki et al., 2012; Belehaki et al., 2015) added a He^+ component and an optimization procedure to fit HT , H_p (H^+ scale height), and a newly introduced parameter governing the shape of the He^+ contribution. The improvements were validated statistically against over 14,000 ISIS-1 profiles and confirmed via independent testing using the Malvern incoherent scatter radar (ISR). The optimized model reduced RMS errors in profile reconstruction by more than a factor of two and yielded accurate TEC estimates in both the topside ionosphere and plasmasphere. However, the latest TaD version, applies a mathematical model for the bottomside electron density profile, in order to simplify its operation application, especially for the three-dimensional version.

In this contribution, we propose a new ionospheric electron density reconstruction model, the hybrid NeQuick-Digisonde-TaD model (HyNT), based on the TaD extrapolated 3D bottomside electron density grids, which are calculated with the NeQuick model, updated with Digisonde bottomside electron density profiles. The results of the new model are validated with Swarm in situ data and COSMIC Radio Occultation profiles.

Section 2 presents the methodology applied to develop the HyNT model. The evaluation and validation results are presented in Section 3. The results are discussed in Section 4.

2.The HyNT model

In this section we present in details the development and operational deployment of the HyNT model.

2.1 The HyNT (Hybrid NeQuick-TaD) model

The HyNT model is developed applying the procedure presented in Figure 1. The whole development relies on the NeQuick as the background model in three dimensions, i.e. latitude, longitude, altitude. The 3D NeQuick grids, are updated with the electron density profiles extracted from ionograms up to the hmF2 altitude. This update is achieved with interpolation, as described in section 2.2. The resulted 2D grid of foF2 and hmF2 and the corresponding GNSS-TEC maps are used as input to the TaD model, to obtain the extrapolated profile at each grid point.

Figure 1. The HyNT model development methodology, composed by the NeQuick model, the Digisonde profiles Ne(h) and the TaD model, adjusted to the corresponding TEC data.

2.2 Interpolation Method

The HyNT model uses an interpolation method for the bottomside, to adapt the available Digisonde stations measurements to the NeQuick model. The specific interpolation method uses a weight factor W , according to the longitudinal and latitudinal distances dx and dy and the respective longitude and latitude degrees to distance factors CRX and CRY and decays exponentially with distance square values in longitude and latitude (Stanislawska et al., 2004).

$$\text{HyNT (Interpolated_value)} = (1-W) * \text{NeQuick_value} + W * \text{Digisonde_value}$$

The mapping scheme applied uses a specific technique that fits the background NeQuick model to the set of Digisonde measurements (Stanislawska et al., 2000, Stanislawska et al., 2001). To avoid numerical instabilities and ensure higher accuracy, additional data are added from the background model during the interpolation procedure. This may be seen as a retrogression to information from the past.

Model input parameters are:

1. two-dimensional function $f(\varphi, \lambda)$ representing the model of the monthly medians, where φ and λ are the coordinates of the point on a sphere where the model is improved,
2. N measurement points $g_i = g(\varphi_i, \lambda_i)$, where (φ_i, λ_i) are the coordinates of the i th point where the parameter is measured
3. Weighting functions $w_i = w(\varphi, \lambda, \varphi_i, \lambda_i)$ which are a measure of statistical dependence of the parameter between points (φ, λ) and (φ_i, λ_i) . The weight $w_i = 1$ when $(\varphi_i, \lambda_i) = (\varphi, \lambda)$ and $0 \leq w < 1$ when two points do not coincide. In a simplest case w is a function of the distance between two points.

When this model is combined with observational data we obtain the function $f^*(\varphi, \lambda)$, where φ and λ are point coordinates on the sphere over which the model is updated. The function f^* has the form:

$$f^* = f + \sum_{i=1}^N (g_i - f_i) w_i^*$$

where

$$w_i^* = w_i \frac{s_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N s_j}; \quad s_j = \frac{w_j + \varepsilon}{1 - w_j + \varepsilon}; \quad \varepsilon - \text{small number of the } 10^{-6} \text{ order}$$

g_i - experimental values equal to $g(\varphi_i, \lambda_i)$

f_i - parameter value from the model at an experimental point equal to $f(\varphi_i, \lambda_i)$,

w_i - factor of influence of a data point on the model equal to $w(\varphi, \lambda, \varphi_i, \lambda_i)$

The variables s_i are values similar to w_i but in the range $(0, +\infty)$. The weight w_i^* , like w_i , is a measure of the influence of the data at the point (φ_i, λ_i) on the model at φ, λ with the screening effect of all other data points considered. If there is only one data point ($N = 1$) then the corrected weighting function w^* is equal to the original w . When there are more data points, but when close to one of them and far from all the others, then the weighting factor w_i^* representing the influence of this closest point, is almost equal to the original w_i . A screening effect can be observed: close to one of the data points the weighting factors w_i^* from remote data points are reduced in comparison with w_i . For two points closed in space one to the other and characterized by the same values, they carry redundant information. Thus the resultant f^* returns the same value when either one or both data points are inserted into the equations.

In the simplest approach weighing functions depend on the distance of the queried point from all observations. This dependency is anisotropic, i.e. measurement points that have the same correlation coefficient are described by geographical coordinates (longitude and latitude) and lie on the edges of the ellipsis. Anisotropy is formulated $CRX \neq CRY$ (correlation radius is measured between points ordered longitudinally (CRX) and latitudinally (CRY)). The correlation radius is the distance between two points for which the correlation between ionospheric characteristics is 0.5. The adapted weighting function has the form:

$$W = \exp [- (dx/CRX)^2 - (dy/CRY)^2]$$

where dx and dy are the longitudinal and latitudinal distances between the queried and measurement points.

2.3 The operational implementation of the HyNT model

The model applied in the European region, using as input data from the ten Digisonde stations of the European Ionosonde Network DIAS (European Digital upper Atmosphere Server): AT138 (Athens, Greece), DB049 (Dourbes, Belgium), EA036 (El Arenosillo, Spain), EB040 (Roquetes, Spain), JR055 (Juliusruh, Germany), PQ052 (Pruhonice, Czechia), RL052 (Chilton, UK), RO041 (Rome, Italy), SO148 (Sopron, Hungary), TR170 (Tromsø, Norway). TEC data are obtained from the TEC maps provided by the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre with Open Access, which also provides access to the SSN and F10.7 indices from the Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the Kp index from the GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences. The operational version of the model is implemented in Python, and the results are provided in real-time in the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre.

The model uses the SSN index as input to the NeQuick algorithm which in turn produces the estimated Electron Density (ED) profiles for each 2D grid location. The Digisonde-derived profiles are utilized for the data fitting and interpolation algorithm to refine the NeQuick initial output and generate the 3D ED profiles. The NeQuick 3D output is used to compute a number of derived (2D grid) ionospheric parameters (foF2, Hm, NmF2, hmF2), which along with the TEC data (2D grid) and the F10.7 and Kp indices, feed the TaD algorithm; as an outcome, iteratively, for each 2D grid location, the relevant estimated electron density profiles are generated. The hmF2 parameter is employed for the classification of the bottomside and topside Ne(h) profiles, i.e the HyNT output.

The HyNT model output has temporal resolution of 15 minutes and spatial resolution of 1 degree in latitude and longitude, with variable altitudinal resolution (10km for altitudes between 100km and 1000km, 20m for altitudes between 1000km and 2000km, 50km for altitudes between 2000km and 5000km, 100km for altitudes between 5,000km and 10,000km, and 200km for altitudes between 10,000km and 20,000km).

3D grids of the HyNT model are accessed through the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre (Belehaki et al., 2025), as well as through a dedicated API.

3. Evaluation and Validation

3.1 Radio Occultation Method

Comparison of the HyNT profiles with Radio Occultation (RO) data is used to evaluate and validate the performance of the hNT model. RO is a technique that uses the LEO (Low Earth Orbit) satellite as a receiver and a respective GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) satellite as a transmitter. Considering that the ray path between the LEO satellite and the GNSS satellite passes through the ionosphere-atmosphere medium and with the assumption that the respective medium has a spherical geometry, the use of the Abel transformation provides the electron density N_e as a function of the distance from the Earth's center across the ray path, as $N_e(r) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_r^\infty \frac{d(TEC)/dr_0}{\sqrt{r_0^2 - r^2}} dr_0$, where TEC is the ionospheric total electron

content, calculated according to the phase and pseudoranges of two different GNSS frequency signals, r is the distance between the Earth's center and a respective point of the sight path that is curved due to the ionospheric refraction and r_0 is the minimum distance from the Earth's center across the ray path (Angling et al., 2021).

Radio occultation data are retrieved from the TGRS (Tri-GNSS Radio Occultation System) experiment on board COSMIC-2 mission (Schreiner et al., 2020). TGRS measures the phase and amplitude of GNSS (GPS, GLONASS, Galileo) signals as they are occulted by the Earth's atmosphere. COSMIC-2 is a constellation of six microsatellites. The mission launched in June 2019 (Schreiner et al., 2020). It occupies low-inclination ($\sim 24^\circ$) near-circular orbits around 520–550 km altitude, phased to provide global coverage in low- to mid-latitude regions. Based on this geometry, the COSMIC-2 RO Ionospheric Pierce Point (IPP) latitude range drops within $\pm 37.5^\circ$, with low percentage of measurements at latitudes above 35° , due to the low inclination of the COSMIC-2 satellite constellation orbit. This is valid for the time interval 2023- 2025. Consequently, the coincidence of the satellite IPP with the region covered by the HyNT model is limited. Despite the restricted cases where the COSMIC-2 satellite is over 37.5° latitude, as it is obvious in the COSMIC-2 measurements points map (Figure 1), a correlation coefficient of about 0.7 to 0.8 is considered for distances of about 1000 km north and south (Rush and Edwards, 1976). The distance of 1000 km has the analogy of longitudinal km to degrees of 111 km / deg, that corresponds to 9 degrees. For the specific study, since high precision is required, 6 degrees maximum distances in longitude have been chosen, to be even more precise, with higher correlation coefficient.

The level-2 COSMIC-2 ionospheric profile data used for this study provide the mean sea level altitude, the geographical longitude and the geographical altitude of perigee point, the azimuth angle, the TEC below the LEO orbit and the electron density in el/cm^3 . The

geographical longitude/latitude pairs are changing for each respective altitude due to the ray path geometry that is not vertical over a pierce point. For this reason, for the comparison between IRI and HyNT electron density profile results, the mean latitude and longitude pairs are considered. Taking into account that 6 degrees of longitudinal distance has been chosen as maximum for statistical analysis, a sample of 504 COSMIC-2 satellite passes over the area of interest is collected, as demonstrated in **Figure 2**. The red points are the HyNT and IRI2020 points, the green points connected with purple lines correspond to the respective COSMIC-2 mean latitude/longitudes points and the yellow labels are the respective distances in degrees.

Data Points Locations and Distances (Maximum Distance Used: 6.0 degrees)

Figure 2. HyNT-IRI2020-COSMIC-2_RO data points connected with purple lines and the respected longitudinal distance in degrees with yellow labels.

Figure 3. Comparison of HyNT profiles with IRI models (standards and constrained) and with RO profiles.

In **Figure 3**, two samples of RO profiles taken at 2024/09/23 0800 UT for RO mean latitude 29.69°N and mean longitude 3.76°E across the RO ray path, while the HyNT-IRI2020 coordinates have latitude 34.00°N and longitude 5.00°E. At 2024/06/27 0600UT for RO mean coordinates are in latitude 30.19°N and in longitude -1.73°W, while the HyNT-IRI2020 coordinates have latitude 34.00°N and longitude -1.00°W respectively. The plots include the RO Cosmic 2 data, the HyNT, the standard IRI2020 and the hmF2, NmF2 constrained IRI2020 model, that is the IRI2020 model but constrained with the hmF2 and NmF2 derived from the bottomside electron density profile. The HyNT model fits better the RO data at the F2 peak height, compared to the standard IRI2020 and slightly better for the constrained IRI2020 model but very close. To explain these results, the mean latitudes and longitudes used for the IRI and HyNT calculations and the distance from the IPP RO COSMIC-2 must be considered among other possible limitations.

Finally, the statistical analysis of a sample of 504 pairs gives a significant higher difference of MAE (Mean Absolute Error) by height for the IRI2020 model compared to the RO data. Lower MAE is calculated between the HyNT model results and the RO data (**Figure 4**).

Mean Absolute Error Distribution by Height
(Box Plots with Quartiles + Connected Median Points - HyNT-IRI2020_Standard-IRI2020_F2_Constrained Electron Density Methods)

Figure 4. MAE (Mean Absolute Error) by height bins of 50 km, between the HyNT model results and the COSMIC-2 RO, and the standard and constrained IRI2020, for a sample of 504 points.

3.2 Comparison to Swarm in situ electron density data

For the analytical investigation of the HyNT model performance in the topside, data from the Swarm satellites used. Swarm satellites mission constitutes of 3 polar orbit satellites (high inclination over 87°), the Swarm-A and Swarm-C both in close orbit with an initial altitude of about 460 km and the Swarm-B with an initial altitude of about 511 km. The Swarm satellites are equipped with Langmuir probes to measure in situ the ionospheric electron density (Friis-Christensen et al., 2006). To estimate the predictions of the HyNT model, the resulted electron density grids calculated over the European area (-5° to 40° latitude and 36° to 60° longitude) are compared to coincident Swarm in situ data. The available Swarm measurements are extracted for the corresponding coordinates using the SwarmRequest package from VirESclient. A nearest neighbor distance tree has been used between the available Swarm points and the respective HyNT grid model points, to find the nearest available HyNT longitude and latitude pair grid points to match the Swarm measurement points in the optimum way. The IRI2020 model provides the electron density grids at the same coordinates and spatial and temporal resolution as the HyNT model. The use of mean absolute error applies as a statistical method to calculate deviation between the HyNT model, the Swarm data and the IRI2020 standard and constrained model. Two statistical plots are given (Figure 5 and Figure 6), one for Swarm A and C data with average altitude 459.6 km (which is most of the time above the hmF2) and one for Swarm B with average altitude 500.5 km (higher and closer to the $O^+ - H^+$ transition height). Of course, the $O^+ - H^+$ transition

height is variable and is depended on the latitude, the epoch, the hour and other parameters (Stankov et al., 2003).

Figure 5. HyNT-Swarm and IRI2020 standard-Swarm, IRI2020 constrained-Swarm mean absolute errors (MAE) for Swarm A and C measurements with average altitude 459.6 km.

Figure 6. HyNT-Swarm and IRI2020 standard-Swarm, IRI2020 constrained-Swarm mean absolute errors (MAE) for Swarm B measurements with average altitude 500.5 km.

From the statistical results presented in **Figure 5** and **Figure 6** it is obvious that the IRI F2-Constrained fits better the Swarm data, compared to HyNT and to the IRI Standard model, while HyNT model has a better performance compared to the IRI Standard model. At the lower altitude of 459.6 km, the MAE for HyNT is smaller compared to the MAE for 500.5 km. This discrepancy points to issues that might be relevant to the Topside Sounders Model equations (Kutiev et al., 2006) used for the topside scale height and are based on topside sounder data from the 70's. The MAE values of the two average heights are given in Table 1.

Average Altitude	MAE [HyNT-Swarm]	MAE [IRI2020 standard-Swarm]	MAE [IRI2020 constrained-Swarm]
459.6 Km	1.11e+05	1.75e+05	0.817e+05
500.5 Km	0.976e+05	1.39e+05	0.551e+05

4. Discussion and conclusions

The HyNT model incorporates the concept of the TaD model for the topside ionosphere, upgraded with the ingestion of Digisonde electron density profiles. Comparison with Radio Occultation (RO) data demonstrates improved performance compared to the IRI2020 standard and constrained versions. Comparison with in situ Swarm data shows degraded performance compared to the IRI2020 constrained version but superior performance compared to the IRI2020 standard version.

The comparison with Swarm data was investigated at two different altitudes, at 459.6 km (Swarm A and C) and at 500.5 km (Swarm B). The best performance for the HyNT model was found at the lowest altitude, which is closer to the F2 peak height. This indicates a possible deviation due to the empirical model used for the topside scale height, which is based on the analysis of the topside sounding data from the 1970s. Even though the comparison with RO data shows better performance of HyNT compared with the IRI2020 constrained version, the identification of coincident data with RO contains higher uncertainty because of the distance between COSMIC-2 measurement points and the respective HyNT grid points. On the contrary, for the case of Swarm measurements, the coincidence is very precise in latitude, longitude, and altitude.

The IRI2020 model benefits from continuous improvements by assimilation of global databases, whereas the TaD formulation relies on empirical models derived from legacy topside sounding missions. This partly explains the advantage of the IRI2020 F2-constrained model in comparisons with in situ Swarm data. Nevertheless, the hybridization approach of HyNT demonstrates clear benefits over purely climatological backgrounds and provides a lightweight alternative to computationally expensive assimilation frameworks.

From an operational perspective, the HyNT model delivers three-dimensional electron density fields in near real time with high spatial and temporal resolution, and is already implemented in the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre. This capability makes it particularly relevant for operational space weather services, including HF communication, GNSS navigation, and over-the-horizon radar applications, where real-time corrections to background climatology are essential.

Several limitations and uncertainty sources should be noted. These include possible biases introduced by Digisonde automatic scaling, the limited spatial coverage of RO data at mid-latitudes, and the dependence on empirical topside formulations that may not fully represent present-day thermosphere–ionosphere conditions. Future work should therefore include systematic error characterization and uncertainty quantification, which would improve user confidence in operational outputs.

Another important point concerns the regional focus of the present validation. The model was evaluated over Europe, where dense Digisonde coverage is available. Extending HyNT to global scales requires addressing the sparse coverage of ionosondes in many regions. This

could be mitigated by hybrid use of GNSS-TEC networks, and new AI-based interpolation methods that optimize information propagation from sparse data.

Future validations should explore storm-time and irregular ionospheric conditions, such as MSTIDs, plasma bubbles, and storm-enhanced densities, which have major impact on technological systems. Coupling HyNT with dynamic models of the thermosphere–ionosphere system, or introducing adaptive response to geomagnetic indices, would increase robustness under disturbed conditions.

For future development, the HyNT model could be further improved by ingesting additional topside satellite data, such as Swarm, CHAMP, GRACE, and GRACE-FO missions, and by experimenting with different analytical formulations for the topside ionosphere and plasmasphere depending on local time, season, and geomagnetic activity. Machine learning methods may also play a role in adaptive tuning of the topside scale height, bias correction of Digisonde inputs, and integration of multi-mission datasets. With the growing availability of RO observations, LEO constellation data, and ground-based networks, HyNT offers a flexible framework that can evolve into a powerful next-generation hybrid reconstruction model.

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Data availability statement

COSMIC Radio Occultation data are retrieved from the UCAR CDAAC Data Center according to the instruction made available by the COSMIC group: https://cdaac-www.cosmic.ucar.edu/cdaac/cgi_bin/fileFormats.cgi?type=ionPrf.

Swarm data are retrieved by the ESA Swarm data access facility.

<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/swarm>, and using the python software provided in VirES <https://viresclient.readthedocs.io/en/latest/installation.html>

The IRI2020 software code was retrieved from <https://github.com/space-physics/iri2020>.
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